

PRAGMATIC ASPECTS OF TRANSLATING ADVERTISING TEXTS OF SOCIAL ORIENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Modern linguistics places a lot of emphasis on how writings and human communication that adhere to a specific style and genre function pragmatically. One of the promising directions in linguistics is a thorough investigation of the interplay between linguistic devices and extralinguistic elements in the overall text structure in order to pinpoint pragmatic purposes. In order to exert some sort of impact on the addressee, contact must be formed between the two of them. The study is devoted to the investigation of the origins and elements of the pragmatic potential of Uzbek text and oral communication. The issue of verbal (written, oral) influence on the recipient has been chosen for consideration in the work out of the many areas of pragmatic study.

The pragmatic aspect of the content, which is influenced by the interaction between linguistic expressions, the communicators—the senders and recipients of the message—and the participants in the communicative act, must be taken into consideration during the translation process. The transfer of all of its other components is affected to some extent by taking the pragmatic component into consideration. The relationship between the comparative speech works and the actors in the communicative act—the readers of the texts in the source language and the translating language—is taken into consideration when evaluating the quality of translation. Translation as a bilingual communication act has not, in fact, achieved its goals if the substance of the initial and final texts is viewed differently.

The theory of speech acts (the typology of speech acts, the nature of their functioning), the theory of communication (the interaction of communicative and pragmatic approaches to language), and some general theoretical provisions of pragmalinguistics (the attitude of the addressee to reality, to the message, to the addressee, expressed by the linguistic unit) serve as the theoretical and methodological foundation of the research. According to A. Neubert, the following text types exist: -texts aimed at the native speaker of the source language; -texts aimed at the native speaker of the source language; -texts that fall in the middle of the first and second categories, i.e., those that are primarily addressed to the native speaker but also, and to some extent, to any other audience;

-texts addressed equally to any readership.

Examples of texts that make up the study's subject include some legal decrees, journalistic articles from the area, particularly those that cover significant local events, and domestic advertising. These writings are written specifically for the native speaker of the original language and are based entirely on his psychology, the knowledge at his disposal, and the characteristics of the sociocultural context in which he lives. Such texts don't suggest a recipient who speaks a different language. The focus of the study is on linguistic techniques that guarantee the pragmatic function of spoken and written Uzbek is carried out. the goal of the research. to evaluate the Uzbek text's pragmatic element and explain how it affects the person it is intended to influence. To do this, the following actions must be completed: -correct the conceptual content of the idea of the influence of text and spoken word on the addressee; -study of directed speech acts of texts in the Uzbek language as a component of speech impact; Consider presupposition as an implicit semantic component of an utterance in a text or oral speech. Identify and characterize the pragmatic possibilities of the introductory verb for the addressee's perception of the content of someone else's speech. The work's scientific uniqueness stems from the fact that it corrects the notion of the pragmatic aspect of written text and spoken language in the context of communicative linguistics. Prior to this study, no thorough pragmatic examination of the Uzbek text had been conducted. These writings' effects on the reader are assessed for their constituent parts, substance, nature, and linguistic mechanisms. Aspects of the influence of an introductory verb on the addressee's perception of the content of another person's speech, presuppositions, and implications from the standpoint of their functioning in the implementation of the impact on the addressee are investigated for the first time in a text written in Uzbek. The goals and purpose of the research dictate the research methodology. Research methods are determined by the purpose and objectives of the research. The work used a descriptive-analytical method, providing for the interpretation, generalization of the studied linguistic phenomena in the process of their functioning in the text; the method of component analysis based on dictionary definitions and taking into account the contextual implementation of the meaning of words. At the stage of analyzing the factual material, the technique of text and oral speech analysis was used, in particular, the identification of semantic features, which is aimed at analyzing the meaning of words and sentences, identifying and interpreting linguistic means of influence, establishing their pragmatic essence. The goals and purpose of the research dictate the research methodology. The work employed a descriptive-analytical method that allowed for the interpretation and generalization of the studied linguistic phenomena as they appeared in the text. It also used a component analysis method that was based on dictionary definitions and took into account how words were used in context. The technique of text and oral speech analysis was employed during the stage of analyzing the factual material, specifically the identification of semantic features, which aims to analyze the meaning of words and sentences, identify and interpret linguistic means of influence, and establish their pragmatic essence. The study's practical significance comes from the fact that the findings can be applied to university courses, textbooks, seminars on the Uzbek language's style with stylistic interpretation, linguistic analysis of the text, professionally-oriented teaching of the Uzbek language to university students, and journalism as a way to maximize the text's influence on the addressee, manipulation, and manipulation. Customarily, the

thought is defined that the style-forming guideline of all logical works is objectivity and not categorical, that's , adjusted and proportionate appraisals, generalization, emphasized consistency, prove, exactness and clarity, as well as a centered communicative introduction towards the addressee. The wide utilize of terms and extraordinary lexicon, the conventional propensity to show regulating lexicon and expressiveness, the nearness of an component of a strict composed convention make up the specifics of the fashion of logical works. The desire for the foremost total correspondence of the shapes of dialect to the substance of the articulation leads to the utilize of various terms. The work of the logical and specialized fashion -logical and enlightening -needs a exact language of terms. The tall lavishness of terms within the content is due to the fact that the writings of this fashion require distinguishing proof of objects and ideas. The agent of the profession is recognized, to begin with of all, by his proficient dialect, which incorporates terms. "The term may be a fundamental instrument for proficient considering, proficient advancement of objective action, the foremost critical instrument for logical communication". The tremendous lion's share of terms have a place to the lexico-grammatical course of nouns. The down to business angles of interpretation is one of the most issues within the transmission of substances, that's , objects or marvels related to history, culture, economy and regular life. In interpretation hypothesis, a extraordinary term has developed to assign lexical units that reflect the particular substances of a specific nation and don't have counterparts in another dialect -"non-equivalent vocabulary". To pass on substances, such methods as transliteration (Uzbek Sirt -Russian Syrt), following (Russian counterforce -Uzbek counterkuch) and "explanatory translation": tanbur could be a stringed national melodic instrument with a long neck". We discover various examples of the transmission of substances, in specific, in Aibek's novel "Sacrosanct Blood" ("Qutlug' qon"). Chetan-arba (there's no such word within the illustrative word reference). Chetan arava -"cart with a wicker body". By the way, the word arbaitself could be a borrowing from the Turkic languages. Dehon is deciphered by the word dekhkanin (with substitution of sounds and the utilize of a Russian suffix). Qatiq is deciphered as "sour milk". The word yigit (boy, youthful man) is interpreted into Russian by the word dzhigit (vigilante, well done, dzhigat). The terms ought to give a clear and precise sign of genuine objects and marvels, build up an unambiguous understanding of the transmitted data by specialists. Therefore, extraordinary necessities are forced on this sort of words. To begin with of all, the term must be exact, that's , it must have a entirely characterized meaning, which can be uncovered by implies of a consistent definition that builds up the put of the concept demonstrated by the term within the framework of concepts of a given field of science and innovation.

Conclusion.

Comprehensive consideration of the pragmatic aspects of translation allows not only to establish some regularities that determine the choice of one of the translation methods, but also to expand the range of means used to transfer "non-equivalent" lexical units. First of all, it is necessary to take into account not only the national specifics of the recipient, but also a number of others, his characteristics in particular, the degree of familiarity with the subject. For the choice of the method of conveying realities, it is extremely important to take into account the functional role that they play in a particular message. Taking pragmatic factors into account entails the introduction of additional elements into the text, the exclusion from it of elements that are redundant

from the point of view of a foreign language recipient, as well as a number of semantic transformations.

Translation theory is fundamentally linguistic, closely related to comparative linguistics, ethnolinguistics, psycholinguistics and sociolinguistics.

References:

- 1.Naer V. L. Pragmatics of the text and its components // Pragmatics and stylistics. -M., 1985. -Issue 245. -P.4-13.
- 2.Schweitzer A.D. Translation and linguistics. -M .: Military publishing house, Ministry of Defense of the USSR, 1973.
- 3.Apresyan Yu.D. Ideas and methods of modern structural linguistics. -M. Education, 1966.
- 4.Novikov A.I. Algorithmic model of semantic transformation of texts. Abstract of the dissertation of the candidate of psychological sciences. -M., 1993 .--26p.
- 5.Chernyavskaya V. I. Interpretation of the scientific text. -M: KomKniga, 2006 .--128p.
- 6.Barkhudarov L.S. The process of translation from a linguistic point of view // Conference on the theory and methods of teaching translation. Abstracts of reports. -M.: 1964.
- 7.Molchanova G.G. Semantics of literary text. -Tashkent: Fan, 1988.

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